

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B369
 Date: 10 May 2008
 Take Off: 14:30:30Z
 Landing: 18:11:49Z
 Flight Time 3h41m19s

Campaign: EUCAARI

Operating Area: Baltic Sea & East coast of Sweden

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Roberts	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Latti Lathouwers	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Keith Bower	University of Manchester	y
5	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	
6	CCN / CCM2	Jamie Trembath	FAAM	
7	Cloud Physics	Phil Rosenberg	FAAM	y
8	Wet & Dry Neph / PSAP / Filters / CVI	James Bowles	Met Office	Y/n/y/n/n
9	SWS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester	N
11	2D-S / CAPS / CPI	Dantong Liu	University of Manchester	N
12	PAN / TDLAS / Core Chem	Jim McQuaid	FAAM	N
13	Mission Scientist 2	Claire McConnell	University of Reading	
14	CPI rack 2	Ian Crawford	University of Manchester	
15	Mission Scientist 3	Radek Krejci	University of Stockholm	
16	Mission Scientist 4	Maria Frontosa	University of Leeds	

Flight Track:

B369 Track 10-MAY-08

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B369

Date: 10 May 2008

Project: EUCAARI

Location: Riga, Baltic Sea, E coast of Sweden

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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141035		Start-Up	-.19 kft	181	56'55.48N, 23'58.68E
142505		ASP	-.19 kft	181	Open
143030		T/O	1.2 kft	314	Riga (Latvia)
143318		Event	1.8 kft	223	Zero JW & Nevz
143507	143812	Profile 1	1.8 - 4.8 kft	287	2k'-5k', QNH 1021hPa
143812	144206	Profile 2	4.8 - 1.8 kft	287	5k'-2k'
143932		Video	3.6 kft	251	Start DFC & RFC
144206	144953	Run 1	1.8 kft	252	2k'
144639		Event	1.8 kft	251	QNH 1022hPa
144953	145845	Profile 3	1.8 - 10.0 kft	249	
145846	150720	Profile 4	10.0 - 1.8 kft	263	To 2k', 1000fpm
150721	150814	Run 2	1.8 kft	260	2k', Q1021
150814	150849	Profile 5	1.8 - 2.3 kft	260	2k-2.5k'
150849	151209	Run 3	2.3 kft	260	2.5k'
151209	151542	Profile 6.1	2.3 - -.21 kft	259	2.5k-50', Q1022
151543	152451	Profile 6.2	-.21 - 8.5 kft	268	From 50'
152513	153443	Profile 6.3	8.5 - 0.24 kft	255	To 500'
153443	153558	Profile 6.4	0.24 - 1.2 kft	253	500'-1.5k'
153516		Waypoint	0.54 kft	255	A40
153559	154108	Run 4	1.2 kft	353	1.5k'
154108	154356	Profile 7	1.2 - -.20 kft	006	1.5k-50'
154412	154942	Run 5	-.17 - -.14 kft	013	100'
154727		Event	-.17 kft	010	Heimann Cal
155018	155654	Profile 8	0.65 - 6.0 kft	001	From 50'
155655	155916	Run 6	6.0 kft	012	
155917	160654	Profile 9	6.0 - -.20 kft	006	To 50'
160705	161207	Run 7	-.14 - -.12 kft	012	100'
161014		Event	-.13 kft	010	Heimann Cal
161135		Video	-.12 kft	018	Change Tapes
161342	162355	Profile 10	0.17 - 10.2 kft	203	From 300'
163950		Event	29.0 kft	196	Zero JW & Nevz
174437		Video	24.4 kft	137	End of Tapes
181149		Land	1.8 kft	043	Oberpfaffenhofen
181739		ASP	1.8 kft	000	Close
181757		Shutdown	1.8 kft	000	48'04.68N, 11'17.53E

B369 Track 10-MAY-08

EUCAARI Flight B369
FAAM sortie brief

Saturday 10th May, 2008

1. Pilot 1 (Directflight) – Alan Foster
2. Pilot 2 (Directflight) – Ian Ramsay-Rae
3. CCM (Directflight) – Dawn Quinn
4. Core Chemistry - (FAAM)
5. Flight Manager - (FAAM)
6. CCN –
7. AMS – Paul Williams
8. Cloud Physics –
9. SP2 – Dantong Liu
10. CAPS? – Ian Crawford?
11. SWS/SHIMS – Debbie O’Sullivan
12. Wet Neph – James Bowles
13. Mission Scientist – Keith Bower
14. Mission Scientist – Claire McConnell
15. Mission Scientist Training - Maria Frontoso
16. Guest – Radek Krejci

Other comments:

Take off from Riga: 1400Z

Landing at Oberpfaffenhofen: 1800Z

Operating Area:

T/O from Riga (Latvia), Baltic Sea and off the East coast of Sweden.

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of aged re-circulated pollution centred over the Baltic Sea.

Weather

Forecast predicts high pressure centred over southern Sweden with very weak flow.
Clear skies preferred.

Flight patterns:

1. Take off Riga at 1400Z (no pirouette before take off).
2. Descend to MPA and commence SLR following the route C5-C4
[30 mins, T=0h 30mins]
3. SLR from C4 to A40. Perform saw tooth profiles to determine altitude for SLR
within peak aerosol layer. [40 mins, T=1h 10mins]
4. SLR within aerosol layer following points A40-A39-WP1 (58N, 17E)
[35 mins, T=1h 45mins]
5. Turn and profile to the south to altitude above aerosol layer
[20 mins, T=2h 05mins]
6. Transit at high level and return to land at Oberpfaffenhofen.
[1h 50mins, T=3h 55mins]

Sortie Debrief

Flight Number: B369

Date: 11/05/2008

Sortie Objectives:

In-situ sampling of re-circulated aged pollution forecast to be centred over the Baltic Sea.

Operating area:

Baltic Sea and surrounds: way point routes A26/C5 to A40 to A38 over the Baltic Sea (Riga, Latvia, southern Baltic Sea and east coast of Sweden).

Weather:

High pressure over southern Sweden with weak flow in the Baltic area. Pollution had re-circulated round the north of the high pressure system towards the Baltic Sea. Clear skies.

Summary:

In-situ measurements of re-circulated pollution and aerosol over the Baltic Sea. A low layer of pollution with high concentrations was found below around 3000ft, peaking at 50-100ft in the central Baltic. Several other weaker layers were also found at higher altitudes, extending up to above 10kft, although these appeared to be high in CO and O3 but less concentrated in terms of particles. Several saw tooth profiles and runs at low levels should lead to interesting analysis.

Flight Patterns:

Initial take off from Riga (Latvia) to 4.8kft to allow operators to get to the instruments. We then descended to 1.8kft on route C heading westwards towards and across the Baltic Sea. On finding relatively low aerosol concentrations we performed a profile to FL100 which revealed two separate layers, the first below around 7-8kft with low aerosol concentrations, and the second above 9kft showing increased CO and ozone, but minimal aerosol concentrations. Following this we made a profile descent to 2kft. During this profile the elevated layer with increased CO and ozone appeared at a lower altitude at 8.5kft during this profile, suggesting a sloping layer, descending towards the west. The start of Run 2 at 2kft suggested we were just below the main aerosol layer, so we ascended to 2.5kft for Run 3 to be within the aerosol layer. CCN, PCASP, AMS and the nephelometer all saw higher concentrations at this altitude.

Now over the well over the Baltic we performed a saw tooth descending to 50ft and then ascending to FL85 (P6.1 and P6.2). The lowest part of the profile revealed an interesting layer below around 1.5kft with much higher concentrations being reported from AMS, CCN, PCASP, CO, O3 and scattering. AMS was seeing high concentrations of sulphates and nitrates. A second saw tooth brought us back down to 50ft seeing a similar vertical profile.

We then performed two runs in the low level aerosol, Run 4 at 1.5kft, now running northwards between way point A40 and A39. SP2 saw doubled black carbon here. We descended to 50ft for Run 5 and saw very high concentrations, including on the CO, scattering (50Mm-1), CCN and AMS. Ozone dropped to its lowest yet at around

40ppb due to chemistry in the marine boundary layer. A thick brown layer of pollution at low levels was clearly visible.

A saw tooth from 50ft to FL60 was performed to show the vertical structure on the west coast of the Baltic showed similar structure to previous profiles, with highest concentrations below around 1.5kft and lower concentrations above this in a distinctly different layer. We remained at FL60 for a few minutes to allow a re-boot of the PAN computer, and then a profile (P9) was performed back to 50ft continuing northwards. Some structure was seen below around 5kft in CN, CO, ozone and scattering. The descent to 50ft suggested that we had moved northwards of the main area of pollution, and the brown haze was no longer visible ahead. R7 was performed at 100ft within the lowest aerosol layer, though low concentrations suggested we had moved northwards of the intense low altitude layer of pollution, and we were also close to the east coast of Sweden allowing the possibility of land contamination. Profile 10 took us up to FL110 and showed that most aerosol was below around 7-8kft, although CO and ozone increased suggesting that the elevated aged layer was still present. Above 9kft CO and ozone dropped off rapidly. We then returned to Oberpfaffen at high altitude which marked the end of science.

Problems:

None

CLM

Mission Scientist's Log

On this notice 4
 wet neph profs was
 so not much good
 data.

Flight No B359 Date 11/5/08 Name C. McCONNELL Page 1 of 3.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
143141					T/O No pirouette
143507	P1				to 6.8kft. Layer well mixed
143812	P2				to 1.8kft.
144206	R1	1.8kft			over land.
144953	P3				to FL100. Saw tooth.
1457					scat ~ 20Mm ⁻¹
					~7.8kft change in layer
					CO ↓ O ₃ ↑ PCASP ↓ neph ↓
					>9kft O ₃ , CO ↑, neph ↑.
145846	P4				Descent. Descent rate
					varied to start with.
					~8.5kft CO ↑. Suggests
					sloping layer.
150721	R2	2kft			No aerosol here
150814	P5	2.5kft			
150829	R3	2.5kft			
151209	P6.1	50ft			Saw tooth
					< 1.5kft scat ↑, O ₃ ↑, CO ↑ ^{CCN ↑}
151543	P6.2				Climb to FL85. Highest
					over < 1.5kft. Also some above.
152513	P6.3				8.5kft → 500ft.
153443	P6.4				CCN & PCASP ↑ large
					@ 50ft.
153559	R4	1.5kft			In aerosol layer.
1536					BC doubled

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B369** Date **11/15/08** Name **C. MCCONNELL** Page **2** of **3**.

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
154108	P7				to 50ft
1541					Slip to Right
					~3kft CO ₂ ↑, CN ↑
					Scat ↑ upto ~ 65Mm ⁻¹
156356	P7 R5	100ft			End P7
15642	R5	100ft			AMS hi, CN hi, scat
					~50Mm ⁻¹ , CO hi,
					O ₃ low as in MBL. ^{Vis low,} brown pollution.
155018	P8				50ft → FL60
155855	R6	FL60			Instrument (PAN) needs
					re-booting.
155917	P9	50ft			~5kft - small ↑ in
					args, BC, CN. AMS no
					sulphates/nitrates here
					as in lower layer.
					~700ft CN ↑
					~600ft CO, O ₃ , neph ↑.
					Not nearly as much here
160654	end P9				as prev. profiles.
160705	R7	100ft			Neph ~ 20Mm ⁻¹
					BL top v. low, ~ 1020mb!
					CO ~ 112 ppb
					Air much clearer
161207	R7				End run @ 100ft
161342	P10				30ft → upper airways.

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 369

Date: 10/05/2008	Operator: pdr	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 1 of 1
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:35:30	130	0.1	2	1												Start profile 1	
14:37:20	280	0.1	2	1												FI40	
14:38:12	485	0.09	2	1												FI50 end profile 1 start profile 2	
14:40:00	400	0.09	2	5												FI 30	
14:41:37	450	0.08	2	2												FI 20 end profile 2 start run 1	
14:44:00	450	0.09	2	5													
14:46:00	450	0.09		5													
14:48:00	400	0.09		5													
14:50:00	600	0.09	3	2												End run 1 start profile 3	
14:51:15	500	0.08		5												FI 30	
14:52:30	400	0.08		5												FI 40	
14:53:30	400	0.08		5												FI 50	
14:54:30	300	0.08		5												FI 60	
14:55:30	380	0.08		10												FI 70	
14:56:30	180	0.1		1												FI 80	
14:56:40	30	0.1		0												FI 90	
14:58:47	80	0.11		0												FI 100 end profile 3 start profile 4	
15:00:55	75	0.09		0												FI 80	
15:02:00	300	0.1		0												FI 70	
15:02:55	480	0.09		2												FI 60	
15:03:55	500	0.09		2												FI 50	
15:05:00	500	0.09		2												FI 40	
15:06:08	600	0.09		2												FI 30	
15:07:18	200	0.09		2												FI 20 end profile 4	
15:08:45	420	0.09		2												Start run 3 fl 25	
15:11:00	440	0.09	4	5													
15:12:10	500	0.09		2												End run 3 start profile 6.1	
15:13:40	950	0.09		5												FI 10	
15:15:43	2000	0.08		10												50 ft end profile 6.1 start profile 6.2	
15:18:09	350	0.08		5												FI 20	
15:19:10	230	0.08		5												FI 30	
15:20:25	250	0.09		2												FI 40	
15:21:30	300	0.08		5												FI 50	
15:22:25	250	0.08		5												FI 60	
15:23:20	70	0.08		2												FI 70	
15:24:25	45	0.09		1												FI 80 end profile 6.2 start profile 6.3	
15:27:00	100	0.11		0												FI 70	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.15	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.66		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 369

Date: 10/05/2008	Operator: pdr	DRS Time: 0	DAU1 Time: 0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: 0	Aux1 Time: 0	Aux2 Time: 0	Page 2 of 2
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
15:28:00	500	0.08		2												FI 60	
15:29:12	550	0.08		5												FI 50	
15:30:05	500	0.08	5	2												FI 40	
15:31:15	375	0.08		5												FI 30	
15:32:35	650	0.09		5												FI 20	
15:33:40	700	0.09		5												FI 10	
	1600	0.08		5												50 feet end of profile 6.3	
15:37:00	450	0.09		5												Start run 4	
15:39:00	500	0.08		2													
15:41:08	500	0.08		5												End run 4	
15:43:56	2000	0.08														50 ft	
15:46:00	3000	0.08		5												Large spike up to 10000 in pcasp	
15:48:00	2000	0.08	6	5													
15:50:10	2000	0.08		5												50 ft start profile 8	
15:52:45	100	0.09		1												FI 20	
15:53:53	200	0.09		1												FI 30	
15:55:00	300	0.1		1												FI 40	
15:56:00	150	0.09		0												FI 50	
15:57:00	120	0.09		0												FI 60 end profile 7 start run 6	
15:59:17	300	0.09		1												End run 6 start profile 9	
16:00:39	500	0.09														FI 50	
16:01:25	400	0.1		1												FI 40	
16:02:35	400	0.09		2												FI 30	
16:03:35	600	0.09		2												FI 20	
16:04:40	600	0.09		1												FI 10	
16:06:55	1000	0.09		1												50 ft end profile 9	
16:08:30	400	0.09		2												Start run 7	
16:10:30	400	0.09		1													
16:12:07	400	0.09		1												End run 7	
16:13:44	350	0.09	7	1												Start profile 10	
16:15:35	500	0.09		1												FI 20	
16:16:30	350	0.09		2												FI 30	
16:17:30	430	0.09		1												FI 40	
16:18:30	420	0.09		1												FI 50	
16:19:40	380	0.09		1												FI 60	
16:20:29	290	0.08		1												FI 70	
16:21:30	40	0.09		0												FI 80	
16:22:40	30	0.09		0												FI 90	
16:23:45	10	0.09		0												FI 100 end profile 10	

PCASP Reference Volts = 7.15	FFSSP Reference Volts =3.4	2D2-C End element 1 voltage =	CIP25 End element 1 voltage =
PCASP Flow rate =0.66		2D2-C End element 32 voltage =	CIP25 End element 64 voltage =
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power =	2D2-P End element 1 voltage =	CIP100 End element 1 voltage =
			CIP100 End element 64 voltage =

P.S.A.P. Log

Flight No. **B.369**.....

Date 10/05/08.....

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GMT	Filter Trans.	Flow Rate	B_a x 10⁻⁶	Ph_det levels		Run	Remarks
Set to DRS time	New filter Tr = 1.000	Set to 3.0 lpm				(30s) ? Ave = s	←Preflight
144206	1						
162738	.942	1.96	0	14	42	transit	EOS

Flight:

B369

KEY

Not Fitted

Fitted, Not Operated

Duff Data

Minor Problems

OK

Thermometers

Hygrometers

Cameras

Navigation + Aircraft

Misc Core

Radiometers

Cloud Probes

Aerosol

Chemistry

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B369

Date: 10 May 2008

Instruments

1. INU – not run
2. Digital Video Box – stickle brick no longer holding it up, now resting on keyboard at aft CorCon
3. FFC Window – lots of smudges, will require cleaning on return to base.
4. Digital Video – DFC not recording at start of flight. Restarted Streaming Activator at 0941, then okay.
5. HORACE Displays – FM Flight Summary window “lost network connection” occasionally, suspect due to number of windows open.

Instrument Status roundup

SWS - Okay

Cloud Physics – 2DP noisy, PCASP needs cleaned before Mondays flight

SP2 –Okay

CAPS/CPI /2DS – CAPS CAS side doesn't work, SIP okay, 2DS not run.

Neph/PSAP/Filters/CVI – Filters, some flow through 1um filter, much reduced through 10um filter when both run together. Counter reset button a bit sticky on upper filter counts. Other instruments okay.

AMS – okay

SMPS – okay at low level

CCN – Okay

PAN/ Core Chem – No data from approx 1530Z-1600Z. Rebooted pc at 1556Z then okay.

Aircraft

Nil

ISDN Emails

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Issues

Multiple calls by flight crew to stop talking on Mission Net.

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by

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13:43:42.04 --- - - - -
13:43:42.04 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
13:43:42.04 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
13:43:42.04 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B369
13:43:42.04 --- - - - -
13:44:10.44 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
13:44:14.91 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
13:44:35.17 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:44:35.27 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:44:35.36 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
13:44:44.44 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:44:46.70 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:44:50.62 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
13:44:54.40 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:44:54.44 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:44:56.14 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:44:58.95 SWS - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
13:44:58.95 SWS - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
13:45:00.34 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:45:02.54 USH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
13:45:02.55 USH - - - 50 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
13:45:04.63 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
13:45:07.60 LSH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
13:45:07.61 LSH - - - 600 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 600ms.
13:45:14.99 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:14.99 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:15.00 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:22.06 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:45:26.88 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:45:26.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:45:27.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:45:27.87 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:28.04 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:30.50 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:45:30.57 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:45:31.44 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:31.64 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:45:33.72 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:46:29.76 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:46:34.13 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:46:34.14 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:46:34.43 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:46:35.08 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:46:35.31 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:46:40.98 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:58:44.48 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:58:47.78 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:47.81 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:48.28 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:48.76 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:58:48.94 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:58:54.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:58:55.27 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:55.34 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:55.55 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:58:56.23 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:58:56.41 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:59:02.11 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:59:40.97 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
13:59:45.55 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:59:45.60 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:59:45.97 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
13:59:46.59 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:59:46.74 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:59:52.40 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
13:59:52.85 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

13:59:52.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:53.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:59:53.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:54.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:59:59.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:05:57.90	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:06:02.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:02.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:02.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:03.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:03.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:09.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:11.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:11.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:11.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:06:12.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:12.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:06:18.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:04.23	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:20:10.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:10.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:10.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:20:10.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:11.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:16.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:20:28.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
14:22:08.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
14:23:57.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 2 deg
14:33:01.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 1 deg
14:35:05.71	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:35:12.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2000 to 500 ft
14:35:18.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 5000 ft
14:38:13.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p1
14:38:33.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending profile 2
14:38:41.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:41.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:41.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:38:43.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:38:44.86	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:38:45.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:45.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:45.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:48.76	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
14:38:52.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:52.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:53.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:53.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:53.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:59.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:39:19.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at 0 deg
14:42:09.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p
14:42:15.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 2000 ft
14:44:46.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -1
14:49:55.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** p
14:50:42.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
14:56:05.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3
14:58:46.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p1
14:59:30.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -2
15:07:20.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:07:20.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:07:20.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:07:22.75	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:07:24.47	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:07:27.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:27.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:27.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:49.38	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:07:53.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:53.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

15:07:54.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:54.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:54.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:57.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:57.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:07:58.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:58.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:00.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:08:45.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** cooler at -3
15:08:51.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p strat of run
15:10:09.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:09.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:09.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:11.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:10:13.69	SWS	172.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:10:14.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:14.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:14.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:24.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:10:33.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:33.13	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:33.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:34.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:34.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:38.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:38.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:10:39.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:40.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:40.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:10:57.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:57.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:10:58.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:00.55	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:11:02.24	SWS	-4.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:11:03.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:03.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:03.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:32.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:32.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:33.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:11:35.02	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:11:36.71	SWS	172.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:11:37.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:37.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:37.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:49.44	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:11:49.45	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 50ms to 100ms.
15:11:50.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:52.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:54.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:55.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:12:10.19	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:12:17.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
15:15:52.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** strat of climb
15:15:57.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** ti FL 85
15:22:55.42	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:22:59.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:59.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:22:59.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:00.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:01.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:06.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:10.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:10.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:10.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:23:11.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:11.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:23:17.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:24:57.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile climb

15:25:20.22	---	-	-	-	-	***	profie descen
15:34:45.07	---	-	-	-	-	***	end of pr
15:34:51.65	---	-	-	-	-	***	climbing to 1500ft
15:36:04.29	---	-	-	-	-	***	run at 1500ft
15:41:17.22	---	-	-	-	-	***	start of profilr descent
15:41:22.08	---	-	-	-	-	***	to 50 ft
15:43:58.26	---	-	-	-	-	***	50 ft
15:44:13.81	---	-	-	-	-	***	run at 100 ft
15:49:30.08	SWS	-	-	-	-		Idling
15:49:30.13	USH	-	-	-	-		Idling
15:49:30.16	LSH	-	-	-	-		Idling
15:49:32.01	SWS	174.0	-	-	-		Telescope sent to -6.000
15:49:33.73	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-		Telescope stopped.
15:49:34.73	SWS	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:49:34.75	LSH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:49:34.75	USH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:49:39.21	SWS	-	-	50	-		VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
15:49:39.22	SWS	-	-	-	50		NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 50ms.
15:49:41.03	SWS	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:49:41.98	SWS	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:49:48.42	---	-	-	-	-	***	end of run
15:50:10.50	---	-	-	-	-	***	50 ft
15:50:17.01	---	-	-	-	-	***	climbing
15:52:42.90	---	-	-	-	-		Reset shutters.
15:52:47.20	SWS	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:47.22	USH	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:47.53	LSH	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:48.19	SWS	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:52:48.37	USH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:52:54.06	LSH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:52:55.68	SWS	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:55.72	USH	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:56.13	LSH	-	-	-	-		Dark measurement started.
15:52:56.66	SWS	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:52:56.93	USH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:53:02.60	LSH	-	-	-	-		Manual scene recording started.
15:56:56.16	---	-	-	-	-	***	start of run
15:59:21.88	---	-	-	-	-	***	end of run
16:03:09.94	---	-	-	-	-	***	cooler at -2
16:06:55.75	---	-	-	-	-	***	50 ft
16:07:11.41	---	-	-	-	-	***	run at 100 ft
16:12:10.51	---	-	-	-	-	***	end
16:12:17.50	---	-	-	-	-	***	climbing 399 ft to tutn
16:13:43.00	---	-	-	-	-	***	profile climb from 300 ft
16:24:23.09	---	-	-	-	-	***	end of science

Flight B369 16:28:55

Heading 198 deg Speed 305 knots Height 19.3kft Press 479mb

Lat 57°6.0'N Long 16°36.0'E Wind 157 ms/1/ 359 deg

Temp -23.59C Dewpoint -38.98C

From 16:08:11 to now

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B369:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
Cloud Physics Processing	Processing yet to be completed.
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
Filters	Awaiting confirmation of whether a log was created - Keith Bower
2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI	2D-S / CAPS / SP2 / CPI operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
CVI	No log. CVI was only operated on three flights : B376, B377 & B378
PAN	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	24 Jul 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

2 x Downward Facing Cameras

Further digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b369_142605_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b369_152605_1hz.avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b369_162605_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b369_142552_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b369_152552_1hz.avi
faam-video-ffc_faam_20080510_b369_162552_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b369_142556_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b369_152556_1hz.avi
faam-video-rfc_faam_20080510_b369_162556_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b369_142600_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b369_152600_1hz.avi
faam-video-ufc_faam_20080510_b369_162600_1hz.avi

Problem in conversion of the following file to .avi
faam-video-dfc_faam_20080510_b369_142605_1hz.raw

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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